

THE STARRING ROLE OF EDUCATORS IN DEVELOPED INDIA

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Abstract

The Foundation of a Nation's progress is its educational system. After many years Indian education system is lightened again by the touch of NEP 2020, to take forward the union govt's 'Vikshit Bharat' initiative. The term 'Vikshit Bharat' means 'Developed India'. To achieve the ambitious goals the foundation of a nation depends on the progress of its educational system. The Govt vision to transform the Country into a developed entity by its 100th independence in 2047. In the picture of Developed India, the teacher emerges as a mainstay for progress and Development. This Abstract provides a brief appraisal of the role of teacher and innovative approaches characterizing the paradigm shift in teacher role. As our nation is a diverse Country, there are diverse children with different individual needs, the teacher plays a crucial role to meet the diverse needs of students. Technology Integration in teacher education, holistic development emphasizes, training for digital India and digital pedagogy, including all the students in an inclusive classroom and developing an advanced curriculum. Importance to be given to intelligence in education. This Abstract contributes insights into the journey of a teacher in shaping Vikshit Bharat (Developed India).

Key words: *Developed India, Holistic development, Artificial Intelligence, Inclusive Education.*

2. Introduction

The Foundation of a nation's progress is its educational system. After many years Indian education system is lightened again by the touch of NEP 2020, to take forward the union govt's Vikshit Bharat initiative. To achieve the ambitious goals the foundation of a nation depends on its educational system and educators. History is full of evidence that there is no better weapon than education to change the world where educators are the backbone. In the west, Teachers or Educators are called as the "architect of nation". Truly teachers are the nation

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builders. In Developed India initiative teacher education is given more importance to improve. Teacher's proficiency and competency so they can better meet the demand of their profession and solve the hurdles that are coming on the way to become a India a developed India or viskshit Bharat. Teachers influence people's lives and the growth of nations and society in a variety of important ways.

The primary responsibility for transferring knowledge and academic abilities to students is with their educators. Through the advice they provide, educators play an important part in creating a viskshit Bharat.

3. Rationale of role of educators

Are key figures in shaping the educational experiences and outcome of students, educators have a profound influence not only on the academic development of learners but also on their social, emotional and ethnic growth. Teachers are fundamental to the functioning of educational systems. They facilitate learning provide guidance and contribute to the development of knowledge and skills in students. Research consistently shows that educator's quality is one of the most significant factors influencing student success. By studying the role of teachers one can better understand how their teaching methods engagement strategies and interaction with student affect learning outcomes. Educators need continuous professional development to stay updated with educational trends, Methodologies and tools, educators play a crucial role in addressing the diverse needs of students, including those subject with special educational requirements. A study of their role can provide insights into how teachers can be better equipped to meet these challenges.

4. Objective of role of educators

The objectives of educators in developed India are multifaceted, aiming not only to provide academic knowledge but also to faster holistic development in students. Following are the objectives that guides you educators in their roles across developed regions of India.

- To help students achieve high academic standards.
- Fostering, critical thinking and problem solving skills.
- Educator should cultivate creativity and innovation in students.
- Aims to foster social, emotional and moral development of students.
- Educators aim to create inclusive classrooms, where every students feel valued and supported.
- Incorporating technology in education.
- Facilitating career development and guidance.
- Educators aim to instill a passion for life learning.

- Preparing students for global competitions.

- Enhancing like skill

5. Challenges faced by the educators

In developed regions of India, educators face several challenges. Some of the key challenges for educators in developed India include:

1. Rapid technological advancements:

With the rapid growth of technology, educators must stay updated with, they are skill to integrate digital tools effectively into their teaching methods. However, many educators face difficulties in mastering new technologies.

2. Pressure of academic excellence:

In many developed parts of India, there is significant pressure from parents, institutions and society for students to excel academically. Educators in turn feel immense pressure to meet their expectations.

3. Variety of student's needs:

Classrooms are diverse and students are varying academic backgrounds, abilities and learning styles. Educators often struggle to provide differentiated instructions.

4. Inadequate professional growth:

Many educators in developed India may not have access to high quality ongoing training that is relevant to involving educational landscape.

5. Focus on examination result

The education system remains heavily focused on preparing students for board exams, competitive exams and other assignments. This creates a narrow view of educational success, neglecting areas like critical thinking, creativity and socio- emotional development.

6. Inadequate infrastructure in some areas:

All through developed areas of India have better infrastructure as compared to rural areas. There still be on the disparities in terms of the quality of schools, learning material and basic facilities.

7. Teachers autonomy Vs curriculum guidelines:

There is a tension between the need for teachers to have the autonomy to innovate in their classroom, and the strict guidelines set by educational boards and standardized curricula.

6. Suggestions:

Holistic development

Apart from bestow knowledge, educators are important in taking care of the holistic development of children lead them through the maze of physical cognitive, emotional, moral and psychological challenges. Viskshit Bharat focus is on the holistic growth of a person in all aspects, not just academically, it's aimed to create well-rounded individuals. It promotes expertness and 21st century skills rather than on test book driven rote learning.

Digital Blending

NEP 2020 weights the role of technology in education and the needs for teachers to be digitally literate. Teachers should use digital learning resources, online assessment virtual labs. Educators should use a combination of online and in-person learning. Online teaching, learning platforms should be used by educators to promote active learnings.

Orifical thinking and problem solving

Effective educators promote students ability to think critically and solve problems creatively. These abilities are important for a nation's economic development and competing in the international market.

Professional growth

With their mastery educators tailor their teaching approaches to suit different learning styles, creating a more inclusive and fair environment. The NEP stir up professional development for teachers, helping them stay updated on the latest teaching techniques and innovation.

Adapting diverse teaching method

The educators modify their teaching strategies to accommodate various learning styles. As there a diverse learner the teacher's fosters, an inclusive educational environment, enabling all to succeed regardless of their abilities, interest and needs to provide a personalized learning environment that can help them reach their goals.

Collaborative learning platforms:

Technology facilitates collaborative learning among teachers, enabling them to share best practices, resources and insights. These platforms allow teachers to create and share content and student to work together.

Inclusive education:

In the vision of educational landscape of India in 2047 inclusive education takes center stage with the aims to create an inclusive and equitable education system for all students. Teachers in this type of classroom play a crucial role in identifying the social, emotional, behavioral,

physical and academic strengths of every Child. Educators should provide individualized support and intervention to students who have a particular needs.

Social Integration and promoting civil engagement:

Education play a crucial role in fostering social Cohesiveness and Integration. Educators can help close gap between different population, fostering inclusivity and national cohesion. By teaching children about their rights and obligation as citizens, educators hope to inspire them to take an active role in democratic process.

7. Conclusion:

The role of educators in developed India is shaped by multiple objectives, challenges and suggestions. While educators continue to focus on academic excellence, their responsibilities have expanded to include fostering emotional, social and ethical development, embracing technological advancement and preparing students for a rapid changing world. Ultimately, the role of educators in developed India is integral to creating a generation that is not only knowledgeable but also well rounded, innovative, empathetic and prepared to thrive in a globalized tech-driven society.

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